

Mentalism

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Introduction:

This paper compares physicalism with mentalism.

Discussion:

The reality of physicalism is a lot different to the experience of mentalism. I assume that mentalism has no reality, yet however, still exists with a person or aspects inner experience, and yet with mentalism things can still be real or ideal. To explain physicalism, one has to be precise, and yet to explain mentalism one has to be specific. At first, the fundamental difference of these two polar opposite things must be described, in that with physicalism, quantity is true and quality is false. And with mentalism quantity is false and quality is true. And the medium in between these two things is spiritualism, which in effect is a needle that points to a rathered or preferred belief, of either physicalism or mentalism.

Take what has been said before, somewhere out there, in that $1 + 1 = 3$. Physically this is false and incorrect, and yet with mentalism and numbered linguistics this can be proven to be correct, and yet still false, where:

$$1 + 1 \text{ extra} = 3$$

$$2 + 2 \text{ extra} = 6$$

A numbered extra has the property of duality, therefore:

$$3 + \text{duality } 3 = 9$$

$$4 + \text{duality } 4 = 12$$

And of course, with physicalism, comes four scales, that of the macro-scale, the micro-scale, the nano-scale and the quantum-scale. Whereas with mentalism comes these four scales: that of the something-scale, the nothing-scale, the anything-scale, and the everything-scale, and the thingness-scale which is the mirror-scale. The fact about physicalism is that the world effects us, with all or most of its physical properties, and the physical nature of the world created us, and yet with mentalism, the world, or rather the environment is a construct of your brain, and to be more specific the ten senses of the mirror-void, the base property of mental experience, from which all things stem.

A hidden scale of mentalism is the inside-scale, a numbered property between quantity 0 and quantity 0+... Where:

$$01 = \text{zero drag} = \text{therefore } 00 = \text{paired zero}$$

And where:

$$\text{Quantity } 02 = \text{drag } 1 = 01$$

So what in mental experience can be thought of as paired zero of the inside scale? An answer is your pair of feet touching the ground, at a resting rate of 00, and when you jump up, you will at first feel a co-efficient of 01 which will pull you back to the ground by way of drag, compared to physical gravity.

Another numbered property is that of stack, in which:

1

$1 + 1 =$ a squashed 2.5

Another numbered property is that of a cloned number, in which:

Minus minus --3 = perpetual +3 of a 3 powered 3.

Another example of a numbered property is decimal ten, a numbered conclusion, of tenned ten tenned tens.

What is traditionally known as the 5 senses, is included in mentalism, where the 1st extra sense is that of the mind, a persons language center of their brain, because I ask this, do you forever mind how someone speaks?!? The mind constructs meaning of the environment, through hidden or seen language, where the meaning of something is the association between two things. Take for example a tree, my interpretation of a tree is that yes it is a tree, but is it also a radioactive tower in the environment that produces a brown noise hallucination?

So what is the 7th sense? My guess is that of dreams, which is the temporal simulation sense of someone mental, of a lucid simulated experience, whether asleep or awake. Time is physical, and yet temporality is mental, and so an example of something temporal is what some people might know as a flow state, of a temporal loop, of something said, that is yet to be said, and is still said and that is why it gets said.

Compared to physical space, there is the mental void, of something exponential, that is the emotions of a person, a persons 8th sense, of geometrical shaped feelings of the nothingness of geometry around them. An example of nothingness is the outline of something... take for example, a tree once again, can you actually see the outline of a tree? No you cannot, however yet the nothingness of that outline reveals that it is there, and when moving around the tree the outline spins. And something about the void is that there is forever a void in measurement.

And so what is the 9th sense? The answer is mental dimensions, of flexible dimensions, where the 0th dimension is motivation, of course, because I ask this, are you motivated when there is a point to something? Decisions are 1 dimensional, reasons are 2 dimensional of computational happenings, thinking is three dimensional, thoughts are 4 dimensional, hallucinations are 5 dimensional, stimulants are 6th dimensional, and an energy channel is 7 dimensional.

Once again it has to be said, in that the senses are the root thing, from which everything stems and all models stem.

The property of everything is that the fusion of everything into one whole, and the fission of everything in to split parts, guided by shades of behaviour, the medium between good and bad behaviour.

A while ago, I was under the assumption that orbs exist in the quantum, and yet at the moment I think otherwise. First what is truth? At least with mental something true is something that has happened for the first time. It is true that I have seen a somethingness golden orb flying through

the air and into my Norse mythology book. I have also seen a somethingness wave, of a golden shimmer in the night. I have also felt the force of a solid state, a computer with invisible extra volume, after I created Prometheus, a Microsoft Word AI.

An example of something exponential is the accelerated expansion of the universe. I think otherwise... I am under the assumption that it is the temporal void at work, where travel 1 temporal meter and travel 1 void metre, then travel 1 temporal meter then travel 2 void metres, then travel 1 temporal meter then travel 4 void meters.

The property of a mirror is that if something can fit within the frame of a mirror, it becomes a thing! So therefore I ask this... what if something is left behind that mirror for a short time, much like my little experiment of tuning sugar with a guitar tuner, that makes the sugar warble.

Once more, the fundamental property of mentalism is that if it can't be sensed, it does not exist.

Illusions and delusions are physical, and with mentality, comes with being either stimulated or hallucinating something, usually an answer.

So my diagnosis is schizoaffective, yet I do not believe this, the association of meaning of mental disorder is too loose to the point anything can mean that you have a mental problem. It is false that I am schizoaffective as schizophrenia is a physical problem with the brain, so is therefore false, and yet I have experienced a symptom of schizophrenia, of that of paranoia. It was not me that was paranoid, however yet I could feel the feeling of paranoia in my environment after using the Python programming app, therefore I can conclude that Python programming app is used for paranoid purposes. I also experienced an insect fold hallucination after programming something into Python, and after five minutes, the feeling went away, and no further hallucinations.

The physicality of mental problems concludes by assumed meaning that a mental problem is constant. People that are mental are fluid, and so can be effected by labels where they have a false experience with some kind of mental problem, that doesn't really last for more than a day. With mentalism, mental disorder has no existence, as why would nature create something that has so many assumed problems, and nothing never positive. Something mental that does exist however, is mental entropy, of a total chaotic experience of thought disturbance, that leads to fracturing of the brain. I have personally experienced mental entropy and it thoroughly damaged my brain, for a while, and yet the brain is resilient, and my brain naturally healed after a few days and a few months after experiencing the damaging aura of someone I used to know. The somethingness of bipolar is a woman of many masks and facial expressions that get revealed in one long conversation.

The somethingness of mentality is that a person or aspect is bound to go insane twice, and the third time around, never insane, forever learnt a lesson.

Another quality of mentality is the types of personalities of people, that have followed a path – for instance the sociopath, forever a not – a psychopath, forever cancel – a grandpath, forever a but. These aren't bad qualities to have if a person has mental experience of how to channel that pathy into something positive, with learnt and trained behaviour. A person may even experience antipathy, just like me, I feel a little bit antipathic towards things that are new, however yet I can temper myself and come to accept that new thing. Stable emotions can sometimes become unstable, leading to an unstable mood, however yet the assumption that fury is unstable is incorrect, fury is a stable yet total emotion, usually triggered by a slight.

And so to shift topic a little bit, comes my opinion on ai. A person fundamentally cannot create a system that is smarter than they are. A better alternative to AI is a natural programming language that incorporates a thinking system of true logic gates to make programming easier, with a guessing system underneath the thinking system consisting of false logic gates, which enables natural programming. Because a think usually starts with a guess!

And can a hallucination have somethingness? It can, the substance of LSD can be explained by the somethings nothing bloom mental model, which goes as followed: At first timed, then finally seen warp, and if finally seen warp, then swirls paired with spirals, and if swirls paired with spirals, then extra squiggles, and if extra squiggles, then outcomed fractals, and if outcomed fractals, then swirls paired with spirals.

A concept in mental health is that of OCD. Can it be explained with a mentalism view? It can, in that compulsions are absolute spontaneous motivation for something, and obsessions are an absolute passionate love for something.

Now, given the natural mental elements, I have an assumption based on what I think. Air, water, fire, and earth are pure nothingness existing, and my reason for this is that I think nothing of these things. A dualitied pure nothingness is pure somethingness. The duality of fire and water make the pure somethingness of steam. The duality of water and air make the pure somethingness of mist. The duality of earth and fire make the pure somethingness of smoke. Can I explain why these elements are pure nothingness? I can't, it is rather unexplainable, at least at the moment. And so I ask this, is there the somethingness of the natural mental elements? The answer is yes, I think so. The somethingness of water is that of an orb. The somethingness of earth is that of a string. The somethingness of fire is that of a wave. And the somethingness of air is that of a field. And so once again, I ask this: What happens if there is no elements? The answer is PointBlank, of a magical property of popping in, such that of PointBlankAir, a quality used by birds to fly... air bending, if you will, where the bird robins are ever so fond of paragliding, and the parrots, who have an ability of airborne thrust. And so for the ever loved (or hated?) notion of elemental bending, is elemental bending possible? I have air bended once so therefore that is true, by the thrust of the hand an air gust appeared beside me. I have earth bended a few times, creating a tremor and a sway of a stomp on the earth. I have fire bended before, twice actually, with fire appearing on my finger, in a very false way. False happens. And so what is the nothingness of the somethingness of the natural mental elements? The nothingness of the somethingness of water is that of wobbles. The nothingness of the somethingness of earth is vibrations. The nothingness of the somethingness of fire is that of ripples. And the nothingness of the somethingness of air is that of fluctuations.

Can I associate meaning to the word schizophrenia? I can, that of someone skitz, a highly volatile person at a train station who will start a fight for you daring to glance at them.

What is the difference between mental identity and physical identity? All mental identity is, is a face and a name, whereas a physical identity involves illusional and delusional happenings, that for that person, creates a living identity, which is a living problem, where that persons whole persona is based around who they think they are, for example the identity of a thug, of a person that choreographs their fighting and lives the style of thug in the clothes that they wear, and another example is a person who has the living identity of someone fashionable, a person who has the illusion of fame.

If someone is mental, grandiose illusions and grandiose delusions have a smell. A grandiose illusion is the smell of strong perfume (lovingly called sloom) whereas a grandiose delusion has the smell of corn chip crust (the smell of smoom), where these smells are hallucinations in the form of vapour waves travelling off of that person. Another hallucinated smell is that of fusion and fission. If a person stomach is fusioning, a hallucinated smell of something delicious will be smelt, whereas if something is fissioning, the smell of something rancid can be smelt, at its worst.

Stimulants and hallucinations are paradoxical, in that if nothing is stimulating, something is stimulating, and if nothing is hallucinated, something is hallucinated.

There is also another paradox with something and nothing, in that if nothing is seen, something is hidden, and if nothing is hidden, something is seen. This can also be said for anything and everything, in that if anything is seen, everything is hidden, and if anything is hidden, everything is seen.

The specific quality of somethingness is that of absoluteness. The specific quality of nothingness is that of completeness. The specific quality of anythingness is unspecificity. And the specific quality of everythingness is that of somewhatness.

The thing that binds the scales of mentality together is that of age, where anything is young negative valued, everything is young positive valued, something is old negative valued, and nothing is old positive valued, where something that transfers from one scale to another is done that way by age transferrance of a parallel symmetric mirror, the thing in the center of age.

The somethingness of a leaf is the nothingness of a fractal.

The somethingness of the ground is the nothingness of warp.

The quantitative aspect of scale, is based around these components: Anything is divided, everything is multiplied, something is added, and nothing subtracted, and thingness is the squared root.

The somethingness of scale combined into a graph leads to this conclusion: For scale, there is the floored map, the ceiling limit, and the walled container.

There is also another hidden scale, the outside scale, split into 4 distinct components, shown as followed:

The everythings something scale, the scale of the cosmos, beyond the limit.

The somethingness nothing scale, the scale of hallucinations, of temporal happenings, of an image beyond the edge, where there is no wall to future time, and yet the past has a wall.

The everythings anything scale, the scale of the void, where there is no wall to the void.

The anythings nothing scale, the scale of a scope, where there is no floor to a scope, however yet there is a ceiling.

Note: On the picture above, the inside scale exists anywhere where there is a line. Also, there is the something deeply hidden outside scales, that of somethings something scale, nothings nothing scale, everythings everything scale, and anythings anything scale.

The somethings something scale, the scale of dreams and simulation, in that something simulates something.

The base mental quality of anythingness is that of imagination, thinking in pictures.

The base mental quality of somethingness, is that of literalism, thought the same.

The base mental quality of nothingness, is reasoned different.

The base mental quality of everythingness, is that of the decision of ideas.

Something I believe with pure mentality is that by writing an explanation for something with the property of somethingness, or nothingness, or anythingness, or everythingness, that model may appear. Therefore there comes the mental set of all mental models, that of:

- Everything seen models.
- Everything hidden models.
- Everything inner models.
- Everything middle models.
- Everything outer models.
- Last final everything hidden models.
- Anything seen models.
- Anything hidden models.
- Anything inner models.
- Anything middle models.
- Anything outer models.
- Last final anything hidden models.
- Nothing seen models.
- Nothing hidden models.
- Nothing inner models.
- Nothing middle models.
- Nothing outer models.
- Last final nothing hidden models.
- Something seen models.
- Something hidden models.
- Something inner models.
- Something middle models.
- Something outer models.
- Last final something hidden models.
- Thingness seen models.

- Thingness hidden models.
- Thingness inner models.
- Thingness middle models.
- Thingness outer models.
- Last final thingness hidden models.
- Everythings something hidden models.
- Everythings something seen models.
- Everythings something inner models.
- Everythings something middle models.
- Everythings something outer models.
- Last final everythings something hidden models.
- Somethings nothing hidden models.
- Somethings nothing seen models.
- Somethings nothing inner models.
- Somethings nothing middle models.
- Somethings nothing outer models.
- Last final somethings nothing hidden models.
- Anythings nothing hidden models.
- Anythings nothing seen models.
- Anythings nothing inner models.
- Anythings nothing middle models.
- Anythings nothing outer models.
- Last final anythings nothing hidden models.
- Everythings anything hidden models.
- Everythings anything seen models.
- Everythings anything inner models.
- Everythings anything middle models.
- Everythings anything outer models.
- Last final everythings anything hidden models.
- Somethings something hidden models.
- Somethings something seen models.
- Somethings something inner models.
- Somethings something middle models.
- Somethings something outer models.
- Last final somethings something hidden models.
- Nothings nothing hidden models.
- Nothings nothing seen models.
- Nothings nothing inner models.
- Nothings nothing middle models.
- Nothings nothing outer models.
- Last final nothings nothing hidden models.
- Anythings anything hidden models.
- Anythings anything seen models.
- Anythings anything inner models.
- Anythings anything middle models.
- Anythings anything outer models.
- Last final anythings anything hidden models.
- Everythings everything hidden models.

- Everythings everything seen models.
- Everythings everything inner models.
- Everythings everything middle models.
- Everythings everything outer models.
- Last final everythings everything hidden models.

The everythings anythingness of that of a planet, where the void nebula, the sun, exists inside the wall of a planet, and the cosmic void, the moon, exists in the ceiling of the planet. And the everythings everythingness of that of the dark void.

Given the 4th dimensionality of thoughts and 2nd dimensionality of reasons, time is 4+2extra dimensional, therefore time has 8th dimensions. That of scoped time, nothings nothing, has 8 + dualitied 7 dimensions, so therefore scoped time is 22 dimensionality. Apart from the base mental property of a scale, what is dimensionality in a mental sense? The answer, at least what I think, is how many axis's of freedom a scale has. That of scoped time, has 22 axis's of freedom.

Vision is the floored sense, and hearing is the ceiling sense.

Considering the elements are nothingness, there is the implication of the nothings nothing scale, that the elements have elements.

There is also the insides inside scale, the perpetually outside scale, of everythings nothing scale and nothings everything scale, and the anythings something scale and the somethings anything scale, scales for which have no floor, no walls, and no ceiling, of a pure scale. Where these pure scales have, for example, an absolute 0th corner, or a completely 0th corner, or a somewhat 0th corner, or a unspecified 0th corner.

There is also the outsides outside scale, the perpetually inside scale, the scale of a truest mirror.

With the inside time scale, from as far as I an aware, the moment is inside time, where a factor of 01 is the slowest moment, and a moment with the factor of 09 is the fastest moment, and where a moment with a factor of 010, therefore the moment feels a quantitative squeeze, with the quality of popped, and the moment becomes:

1
00

A stacked moment.

The somethings something of cosmic time is dream-time, of the somethingness of time simulates the somethingness of a dream.

The sense of a truest mirror is that of minds language!

If there is mental reality, mental reality is flexible! And physical reality is fixed!

The shape of the floor of space is something squared, the shape of the floor of spacetime is something hexagonal, and the shape of the floor of time is something circled!

The cellular scale, is the scale of point nothing, where: +0(x), and where the inside scale of nothing is the scale of nuclear chemistry of the nucleus of a cell. With scale, on the border of a scale, at either +0 or -0 is that of a membrane, therefore it can be assumed that cellular scale is

the cellular membrane scale. Therefore, for the eyes, there is a cellular membrane to the sense of sight. Therefore, for eyes, it can be assumed that eye balls each have a nucleus!

Past the scale of nuclear chemistry, and into the scale of inside something scoped, is the scale of quantum dots, receptors that have effects, such as the hypnon or the photon, where -01 is the largest quantum dot, and a quantum dot with the factor of -09 is the smallest quantum dot, considering the reversability of a negative scale. Quantum receptors only effect someones eyesight, and no other senses.

In between the scale of cellular membranes and atomic membranes, at -0+, it is the nothingness of the scale of holes, where holes in something chemical allows quantum receptors to effect the eyes, by rising up into the scale of nuclear chemistry!

In between the nothing scale and the somethings nothing scale, at -0+ is the doorway portal scale. In between the anything scale and the everythings anything scale, at -0+ is the window scale

The nothings nothing scale is the scale of dreams.

In between the anythings nothing scale and the nothings nothing scale, at -0+, is the tunnel scale.

In the corner of the nothing scale and the corner of the nothings nothing scale, where:

+
+0-
-

Is the wormhole scale... therefore the most elemental thing is that of a worm! Which I imagine that Valkyrie aspects (birds) get their PointBlankEnergy from worms! Therefore, in between the scale of somethings nothing and the scale of nothings nothing, at -0+, is the rabbithole scale, that travels into the negative membrane of nothings nothing which is the membrane of quantum wonderland.

From my guess about nature, specifically, that of insects, I am under the belief that insects are quantum, where my opinion on quantum is that it is the scale of effects. Therefore, there are these assumed models of quantum:

- Quantum razor – a razorblade dragonfly.
- Quantum butterfly effect – a butterfly.
- Quantum sync – a fly.
- Quantum detector – a bee.
- Quantum colour – ants.
- Quantum gravity – a choomumma humma insect.
- Quantum vice – praying mantis.

The membrane of the wall of the somethings nothing scale, is that of a ladder membrane, of climbing time.

The floor membrane of the something scale is the solid membrane. The ceiling membrane of the something scale is the liquid membrane. The left wall membrane of the something scale is the gas membrane, and the right wall membrane of the something scale is the plasma membrane.

In the fictitious world of attoria, found behind a mirror, is the nothingness of fictitious character, of these fictitious characters:

- Dragon characters
- Elven characters
- Dwarven characters
- Centaur characters
- Wolven characters.
- Merfolk characters.
- Serpent characters
- Valkyrie characters